

Chemical constituents of *Polyalthia suberosa* Thw.

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Chemical studies of stem bark of *Polyalthia suberosa* (Annonaceae), led to the isolation of two compounds which were characterized as 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-butane-2-ol (1) and 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-butane-2-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (2) on the basis of spectroscopic studies.

Annonaceus plants are known to be a rich source of bio-active substances¹. The genus *Polyalthia* (family : Annonaceae) is a shrub or small tree², found throughout India. *P. suberosa* (Hindi : chamkhirni) is used as an abortifacient in Phillipines³ and found to be reported for an anti-HIV compound⁴. Earlier investigators had reported the isolation of some triterpenes⁵ (suberosal, α -amyrin and β -amyrin) and lanuginosine⁶, an oxoaporphine alkaloid from this species. We report herein, the isolation and characterization of 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-butane-2-ol (1) and its glycoside (2) for the first time from this plant species and from family annonaceae itself. A search of literature has revealed that 2 had been earlier reported from *Abies webbiana*⁷ (family : Pinaceae).

The methanolic extract obtained from the stem bark of *P. suberosa* was column chromatographed and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. The benzene and EtOAc : MeOH eluates yielded two compounds, compound I (1) and compound II (2) respectively.

Compound I (1) : Colourless needles, m.p. 76–78°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ –16.8 (MeOH), C₁₁H₁₆O₂, (M⁺ at *m/z* 180) showed IR band at 3500 cm⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹ for hydroxyl and aromatic functionalities. It showed ¹H NMR signals at δ 3.78 (3H, s) for aromatic methoxy group and at δ 6.82 and 7.11 (2H, d each, *J* 8.4 Hz) which suggested the presence of 4-methoxyphenyl unit in I. The presence of a carbinyl hydrogen (δ 3.80, sextet, *J* 6.2 Hz) a methyl bound to oxycarbon (δ 1.21, 3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz) and two vicinal methylene groups at δ 2.65 and 1.72 (2H, m each) suggested the presence of 4-aryl-2-oxygenated butane. Acetylation of I yielded monoacetate (1a) C₁₃H₁₈O₃ (M⁺; 222), IR of which showed absence of hydroxyl absorption. The signal of carbinyl hydrogen in I moved downfield to δ 4.78 (1H,

sextet), clearly suggested the presence of hydroxyl group at C-2 position in I. Hence, compound-I is 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-butane-2-ol (1).

- 1 R = H
1a R = Ac
2 R = Glucopyranosyl

Fig. 1

Compound II (2) : C₁₇H₂₆O₇; amorphous powder, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ –22.6° (MeOH) showed strong IR absorption for hydroxyl (3600–3300 cm⁻¹) and aromatic (1600 cm⁻¹) groups. The presence of 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-oxygenated butane group was evidenced by the ¹H NMR data δ 6.98 and 7.31 (2H, d each, *J* 8.4 Hz), 3.91 (3H, s), 3.80 (1H, sextet), 2.85 (2H, m), 2.08 and 1.88 (1H, m each) and 1.39 (3H, d). In addition to these signals the spectrum also showed signal for one anomeric hydrogen δ 4.57 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz) and several oxygenated hydrogens between δ 3.44 and 3.91 as a complex multiplet. The presence of large number of oxygen atoms in the molecule, strong hydroxyl absorption in IR spectrum and signals for several oxygenated hydrogen and one anomeric hydrogen doublet (δ 4.57, *J* 7.8 Hz) in ¹H NMR spectrum had prompted us to assume the glycosidic nature of II. This assumption was verified by acid hydrolysis of 2, which yielded D-glucose as glycone and aglycone was found to be identical with 1 on 400 MHz spectral comparison. Therefore, 2 was characterized as 2-

glucopyranosyl-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-butane.

Experimental

The plant material was purchased from M/s United Chemical & Allied Products, 10, Clive Row, Kolkata, India and a specimen sample had been preserved in the Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India.

Melting points were uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a JASCO IR-130 spectrometer. UV spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV 200 spectrometer using spectral methanol. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded using Bruker AMX 400 spectrometer at 400 MHz with TMS as an internal standard. Optical rotations were recorded on a Yanoco-OR-50 automatic polarimeter (cell length 1 cm). EI-MS were recorded on MS-50 instrument with direct inlet. Silica gel used for column chromatography refers to Centron Research Laboratories (India) 70–325 mesh. TLC was carried out on silica gel-G (Merck) in different solvent systems.

The dried and milled stem bark (2.5 kg) of *Polyalthia suberosa* was extracted successively with *n*-hexane and methanol (101) for 48 h in a soxhlet extractor. The methanol extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The extract (35 g) thus obtained was chromatographed over a column of silica gel and eluted using *n*-hexane, benzene, mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate, ethyl acetate and a mixture of ethyl acetate-methanol in increasing polarity.

4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)butane-2-ol (1) :

Benzene eluate yielded colourless needles (275 mg), m.p. 76–78°, C₁₁H₁₆O₂, [α]_D–16.8° (MeOH); IR (ν_{max}) (CHCl₃) 3300, 1600 cm⁻¹; UV (λ_{max}) (MeOH) 251 nm; ¹H NMR (400 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 1.21 (3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz, C-1-H₃), 1.72 (2H, m, C-3-H₂), 2.65 (2H, m, C-4-H₂), 3.78 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.80 (1H, sextet, *J* 6.2 Hz, C-2-H₂), 6.82 and 7.11 (2H, d each, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H₂ each); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_c 23.60 (q, C-1), 31.13 (t, C-3), 41.05 (t, C-4), 55.22 (q, Ar-OCH₃), 67.46 (d, C-2), 113.76 (d, C-2'), 129.22 (d, C-3'), 134.08 (s, C-1'), 137.71 (s, C-4').

Acetylation of 1 to 1a :

A mixture of 1 (25 mg), Ac₂O (0.5 ml) and pyridine (0.2 ml) was kept overnight under anhydrous condition at room temperature. The reaction mixture after usual work up yielded 1a, a waxy solid, C₁₃H₁₈O₃, IR (ν_{max}) (CHCl₃)

1735, 1130, 1065 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 1.25 (3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₃CHO-), 1.76 (2H, m, 1 × CH₂), 2.72 (2H, m, Ar-CH₂), 3.83 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 4.78 (1H, sextet, -CHOAc-), 6.73 and 7.13 (2H, d each, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H₂ each).

2-Glucopyranosyl-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-butane (2) :

Ethyl acetate-methanol (19 : 1) eluates yielded 2, as amorphous powder (210 mg), C₁₇H₂₆O₇, [α]_D–22.6 (MeOH); IR (ν_{max}) (KBr) 3600–3300, 1600 cm⁻¹; UV (λ_{max}) (MeOH) 251 nm; ¹H NMR (400 MHz; CD₃OD) δ 1.39 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, CH₃-CHO-), 1.88 and 2.08 (1H each, m, -CH₂-CH₂-CH-), 2.85 (2H, m, Ar-CH₂-CH₂), 3.44 (1H, sextet, C-2-H), 3.51 (1H, m, C-5-H of sugar), 3.68 and 3.78 (1H each, dd, C-6-H₂), 3.75 (3H, m, C-2-H, C-3-H, C-4-H), 3.91 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 4.57 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, anomeric-H), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H₂), 7.31 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H₂).

Acid hydrolysis of compound II :

Refluxing a solution of 2 (25 mg) in 2 *N* methanolic HCl (10 ml) for 2 h, following the usual work up yielded the glycone part and aglycone part. The glycone part was identified as D-glucose by co-PC and TLC studies. Aglycone part was identified as 1, by m.p, co-PC, TLC, specific rotation and 400 MHz ¹H NMR spectral comparison.

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